

Harmonic Force Fields and Force Constants of Prebiotic Aminomalononitrile and Diaminomalononitrile by Using DFT and SQMFF Calculations

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Abstract:

Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations and scaled quantum mechanical force field (SQMF) methodology have been used to perform the harmonic force fields and force constants of prebiotic aminomalononitrile and Diaminomalononitrile of diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and diaminefumaronitrile (DAFN) because they are related by the DAMN \leftrightarrow DAFN photoisomerization equilibrium. Hence, full vibrational assignments and its scaled force constants are reported. Comparisons of predicted spectra with the experimental FTIR, FTRaman, ^1H , ^{13}C -NMR and UV-visible spectra show good correlations. The IR and Raman spectra show bands related to the two forms. Frontier

orbitals studies suggest that both forms are more reactive in solution while that DAFN presents higher reactivity in this medium. These results agree with the lower stability observed for DAFN in solution by NBO study and with its lower energy observed by MEP surface. Higher scaled force constants values of DAMN suggest its higher stability in solution, as supported by the lower values of its geometrical parameters.

Keywords: *Diaminomaleonitrile, diaminefumaronitrile, molecular structure, harmonic force fields, vibrational analysis, DFT calculations.*

Introduction

Diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) is the tetramer of hydrogen cyanide and, is a versatile reactive that has been used from long time in the synthesis of organic and bioorganic reactions of great interest in prebiotic chemistry, such as syntheses of heterocyclic systems, pharmaceuticals, chemosensors, polymers, complexes, purine nucleobases including conjugated functional materials for electroluminescent devices (Mendelson, et al., 1954; Webb, Frank, &

Schneider, 1955; Yamada, et al., 1968; Becker, Kolc, & Rotham, 1973; Stephen-Sherwood, & Oró, 1973; Begland, et al., 1974; Koch, & Rodehorst, 1974; Sidorov, et al., 1999a; Sidorov, et al., 1999b; Al-Azmi, Elassar, & Booth, 2003; de Oliveira, et al., 2021; Wang, et al., 2003; Anitha, et al., 2013; Devi, & Singh, 2013; Szabla, et al., 2014; Doomanlou, et al., 2018; Méndez-Mendoza, & Ruíz-Guerrero, 2018; Shu, et al., 2019; Aruna, et al., 2019; Hortelano, Ruiz-Bermejo, & Fuente, 2021; Ruiz-Bermejo, et al., 2022). Structurally, two *Cis* and *Trans*

conformers are expected for DAMN, as observed in Fig. 1. The *Cis* form is known as DAMN while the *Trans* one as diaminofumaronitrile (DAFN) and, both conformers are related between them because when a solution of DAMN in acetonitrile is irradiated with ultraviolet ray (295-335 nm) during 7 hours the DAFN form is obtained (Yamada, et al., 1968; Szabla, et al., 2014). Hence, a high quantum yield with very small activation energy is observed in the *Cis* ↔ *Trans* photoisomerization (Becker, Kolc, & Rotham, 1973). In acid, basic or neutral solutions the *Trans* form is reverted to the *Cis* one (Yamada, et al., 1968). DAMN was used in the syntheses of bioorganic molecules, of derivatives with potential anti-chagasic properties and in the formation of complexes with potential antibacterial and antifungal activities (Stephen-Sherwood, & Oró, 1973; Begland, et al., 1974; Koch, & Rodehorst, 1974; Sidorov, et al., 1999a; Sidorov, et al., 1999b; Al-Azmi, Elassar, & Booth, 2003; de Oliveira, et al., 2021; Wang, et al., 2003; Anitha, et al., 2013; Devi, & Singh, 2013; Szabla, et al., 2014; Doomanlou, et al., 2018). Recent studies based DAMN derivatives evidence the generation of conjugated polymers functional materials to fabricate chemosensors and fluorophores (Shu, et al., 2019; Aruna, et al., 2019; Hortelano, Ruiz-Bermejo, & Fuente, 2021; Ruiz-Bermejo, et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Structures of *Cis* and *Trans* Forms of Diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and Diaminofumaronitrile (DAFN), Respectively

The molecular structure of *Cis* form DAMN was determined by Sidorov et al while Yamada et al the structure for the *Trans* one, DAFN (Yamada, et al., 1968; Sidorov, et al., 1999a). The existence of two donors NH₂ and of strong acceptors of H bonds in DAMN and DAFN play important roles on its properties, reactivities and biological activities. So far, few spectroscopic and theoretical studies associated to structural, topological and vibrational properties of DAMN and DAFN are reported yet. In this context, the aims of this work are to study the theoretical structures of DAMN and DAFN in gas phase and aqueous solution by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations, to predict their properties, reactivities and behaviours and to perform the assignments of all vibration modes of both conformers with the harmonic force fields, normal coordinates analyses and scaling factors. In addition, the scaled force constants of those two species in the different media are also reported. The validation of all calculations are performed by means of comparisons of experimental ¹H, ¹³C-NMR, infrared, Raman and UV-Visible spectra of DAMN and DAFN with the predicted by calculations. These results have allowed predicting reactivities and behaviours of two conformers DAMN and DAFN in the different media and its quick identifications by using the vibrational spectra.

Material and Methods

The *GaussView* program has been used to model the two *Cis* and *Trans* conformers, DAMN and DAFN (Dennington, Keith, & Millam, 2019) while its optimizations in gas phase and water were performed with the Gaussian 16 program by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method (Becke 1988, Lee, Yang, & Parr, 1988; Frisch, et al., 2019). The optimized structures of two *Cis* and *Trans* conformers in gas phase with the atoms numbering are shown in Fig. 2. All calculations in solution and the solvation energies in the different solvents were predicted with the IEF-PCM and universal solvation methods (SMD) (Miertus, Scrocco, & Tomasi, 1981; Tomasi, & Persico, 1994; Marenich, Cramer, & Truhlar, 2009).

Figure 2. Optimized Structures of *Cis* and *Trans* Conformers DAMN and DAFN with Atoms Numbering

The variations of volume were calculated with the Moldraw program (Ugliengo, 1998). Atomic charges and the molecular electrostatic potentials (MEP) were calculated with the NBO 5.1 program and the Merz-Kollman (MK) charges (Glendening, et al., 1996; Besler, Merz Jr., & Kollman, 1990) while topological properties have been predicted with the AIM 2000 program (Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001). The frontier orbitals and some descriptors have been used to predict reactivities and behaviours of *Cis* and *Trans* conformers in the different media (Pearson, 1986; Parr, von Szentpaly, & Liu, 1999). The harmonic force fields determined with the SQMFF procedure was used to perform the vibrational assignments of *Cis* and *Trans* conformers at the same level of theory (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). Hence, the normal internal coordinates of NH_2 groups were taken from a reported work (Cataldo, et al., 2024; Sundius, & Brandán, 2023). In these analyses, we have considered potential energy distribution (PED) contributions $\geq 10\%$.

The predicted Raman spectra for both species have been transformed to intensities (Keresztury, et al., 1993). The GIAO method was used to predict the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of both forms in the different media (Ditchfield, 1974) while the electronic spectra of DAMN and DAFN in aqueous solution were predicted using the Gaussian 16 program (Frisch, et al., 2019).

Results and Discussion

Optimizations of *Cis* and *Trans* Conformers in Different Media

In Fig. 1 and 2 are shown the structures of *Cis* and *Trans* conformers while in Table 1 are given the total energy corrected by ZPVE, dipole moments and volumes of both species in the different media by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations. The E values are corrected by zero-point vibrational energies (ZPVE) due to that the molecules present movements even in the zero K.

Table 1. Comparison of Calculated Total Energies (E), Dipole Moments (μ), Volume Variations (ΔV) and Solvation Energies (ΔG) between the Different Forms Diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and Diaminofumaronitrile (DAFN) in Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Diaminomaleonitrile-Diaminofumaronitrile			
B3LYP/6-311++G** method			
Gas Phase			
Species	E_{ZPVE} (Hartrees)	μ (D)	V (\AA^3)
<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)	-373.8147	6.80	115.7
<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)	-373.8139	1.47	115.9
Aqueous Solution			
Species	E_{ZPVE} (Hartrees)	μ (D)	V (\AA^3)
<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)	-373.8353	10.06	114.7
<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)	-373.8310	2.42	115.2

Note: *Z.P.V.E, zero point vibrational energy

Regarding the results for both species, it is observed that the E_{ZPVE} values show the most negative values for *Cis* form in both media (-373.8147 Hartrees and -373.8353 Hartrees). Probably, the high μ values of *Cis* form justify its higher stability in the two media. Evidently, the presence of both NH_2 and $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ groups in the two conformers but in different positions and media have influence on the dipole moments and volumes because in gas phase both forms show approximately the same V values while in aqueous solution the *Trans* form presents a higher V value (115.2 \AA^3) than the *Cis* one (114.7 \AA^3). Here, the presence of NH_2 and $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ groups in different positions justify the decreasing in the

μ values. When the magnitude, directions and orientations of μ vectors of both forms in gas and aqueous solution are analysed from Fig. 3, changes in these three factors are observed in the two conformers. Hence, the polarity of solvent and the positions of different groups modifies the μ and V values. Note the great magnitude of μ vector corresponding to the *Cis* form and where the vector is located in the centre of $\text{C}1=\text{C}2$ bond and in direction axial while for the *Trans* form the μ vector is in the centre of bond but in equatorial position. Evidently, higher values are observed for the *Cis* form in solution because the donor NH_2 and acceptors $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ groups are possibly hydrated in this medium.

Figure 3. Orientations, Magnitudes and Directions of Dipole Moment Vectors of *Cis* and *Trans* Forms Diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and Diaminofumaronitrile (DAFN) in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Solvation Energies of *Cis* and *Trans* Conformers

Comparison of volume variations (ΔV) and uncorrected (ΔG_{un}) and corrected solvation energies (ΔG_c) of DAMN and DAFN in the two

media by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method can be observed from Table 2. ΔG_{ne} are the corrections due to the non-electrostatic terms determined from optimized PCM calculations.

Table 2. Comparison of Volume (ΔV) and Solvation Energies (ΔG) Variations of *Cis* and *Trans* Forms, Diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and Diaminofumaronitrile in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Solvation energy (kJ/mol)				
Species	ΔG_{un}	ΔG_{ne}	ΔG_c	ΔV (\AA^3)
<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)	-54.0336	25.3726	-79.4062	-1.0
<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)	-44.8531	24.8710	-69.7241	-0.7

Note: ΔG_{un} . See text

Regarding the volume variations from the gas phase to the solution from Table 2, it is observed that both conformers evidence contractions of volume in aqueous solution showing higher values the *Cis* form (-1.0 \AA^3). The uncorrected energy (ΔG_{un}) values correspond to the differences of E_{ZPVE} in solution $-E$ gas phase (Table 1). Here, the solvation energies evidence the diverse hydrations of species. The results show that for both species there is a correlation

between V and ΔG_c , thus, the most negative values are observed to higher V contraction. Hence, the *Cis* form DAMN in water show the highest solvation energy values of -79.4062 kJ/mol . Probably, the higher values observed for the *Cis* form DAMN are justified due to that the NH_2 and $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ groups could be highly hydrated in solution, as observed from the cavity of solvation presented in Fig. 4. DAMN shows higher cavity for the formation of H bonds.

Figure 4. Cavity of Solvation of *Cis* and *Trans* Forms Diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and Diaminofumaronitrile (DAFN) Calculated in Aqueous Solution with the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Structural Study

The experimental molecular structure of *Cis* form DAMN was reported by Sidorov et al while Yamada et al have reported the structure for the *Trans* one DAFN (Yamada, et al., 1968; Sidorov, et al., 1999a). To perform vibrational studies are

important take into account the correlations between the optimized and experimental structures and, for these reasons, the parameters are compared with the experimental determined for both forms by using X-ray diffraction (Yamada, et al., 1968; Sidorov, et al., 1999a).

Table 3. Calculated Geometrical Parameters for the *Cis* and *Trans* Conformers DAMN and DAFN in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution

Parameters	<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)		<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)		^b Exp <i>Cis</i>	^c Exp <i>Trans</i>
	^a GAS	^a PCM	^a GAS	^a PCM		
	Bond Length (Å)					
C1-C2	1.364	1.370	1.368	1.369	1.353	1.294
C1-N6	1.400	1.390	1.398	1.398	1.393	1.376
C1-C10	1.422	1.419	1.426	1.423	1.429	1.465
C2-N3	1.400	1.390	1.398	1.398	1.373	1.446
C2-C9	1.422	1.419	1.426	1.423	1.439	1.440
N3-H4	1.010	1.013	1.011	1.014	0.948	0.831
N3-H5	1.015	1.015	1.012	1.014	1.008	0.854
N6-H7	1.010	1.013	1.011	1.014	0.933	0.971
N6-H8	1.015	1.015	1.012	1.014	0.885	0.887
C9-N11	1.157	1.160	1.157	1.159	1.142	1.145
C10-N12	1.157	1.160	1.157	1.159	1.142	1.136
^b RMSD	0.0508	0.0516	0.0318	0.0332		
^c RMSD	0.0885	0.0903	0.0792	0.0806		
	Bond angle (degrees)					
C2-C1-N6	120.2	122.8	125.2	126.0	124.0	129.2
C2-C1-C10	122.0	119.6	118.3	118.2	118.7	117.5
N6-C1-C10	117.7	117.5	116.3	115.6	117.1	113.3
C1-C2-N3	120.2	122.8	125.2	126.0	124.4	122.1
C1-C2-C9	122.0	119.6	118.3	118.2	117.9	120.5
N3-C2-C9	117.7	117.5	116.3	115.6	117.6	117.5
C2-N3-H4	114.6	114.6	115.0	113.5	121.4	99.7
C2-N3-H5	113.8	115.0	115.1	114.5	113.4	111.2
H4-N3-H5	111.8	111.7	112.4	111.0	124.2	91.9
C1-N6-H7	114.7	114.6	114.9	113.5	112.4	115.5
C1-N6-H8	113.9	115.0	115.1	114.5	117.0	102.9
H7-N6-H8	111.9	111.7	112.4	111.0	114.7	136.5
^b RMSD	4.86	4.39	4.11	118.63		
^c RMSD	11.10	11.01	10.96	115.43		
	Dihedral angles (degrees)					
N6-C1-C2-N3	1.9	4.8	-165.6	-166.5	-2.6	
N6-C1-C2-C9	178.3	-179.2	9.1	8.1	175.3	
C10-C1-C2-N3	178.3	-179.2	9.1	8.1	-177.5	
C10-C1-C2-C9	-5.4	-3.3	-176.1	-177.3	0.5	
C2-C1-N6-H7	-173.2	-165.3	-144.8	-144.9	163.5	

C2-C1-N6-H8	-42.6	-33.8	-11.9	-16.1	27.8	
C10-C1-N6-H7	10.3	18.7	40.3	40.4	-21.6	
C10-C1-N6-H8	140.9	150.1	173.3	169.2	-157.3	
C1-C2-N3-H4 [#]	-173.1	-165.2	-144.9	-144.9	-176.9	
C1-C2-N3-H5 [#]	-42.6	-33.8	-12.0	-16.1	-7.7	
C9-C2-N3-H4 [#]	10.3	18.7	40.2	40.4	5.2	
C9-C2-N3-H5 [#]	140.9	150.1	173.2	169.2	174.3	
^b RMSD	167.6	167.2	166.4	166.0		

Note: ^aThis work, ^bFrom Ref Sidorov, et al., 1999a, ^cFrom Ref Yamada, et al., 1968.

[#]See text. RMSD values in bold letters

Thus, optimized parameters for the two forms are compared in Table 3 with the corresponding experimental ones by using the root-mean-square deviation values (RMSD). On the other hand, the *Trans* form show higher variations in the bond angles in aqueous solution (118.63°). Better correlations are found for bond lengths of *Trans* form in the two media (0.0318-0.0332 Å) while the *Cis* form show lower RMSD values in the bond lengths (4.86-4.39 °). Here, clearly the dihedral angles for the two forms show higher RMSD values in both media due to the signs changes observed for some angles, with exception of the dihedral C1-C2-N3-H4, C1-C2-N3-H5, C9-C2-N3-H4, C9-C2-N3-H5 angles, which remain constants for the two forms in both media. In Table 3, these dihedral angles are differenced by the # symbol. The reasonable

agreements in these parameters indicate that the structures can be used to perform the vibrational analyses.

NMR Study

In the above section, good correlations in structures of both forms are observed, but now the concordances between the predicted NMR spectra for DAMN and DAFN in aqueous solution should be analysed. Therefore, the predicted ¹H- and ¹³C-NMR chemical shifts of both species in aqueous solution by using the GIAO and B3LYP/6-311++G** methods are summarized in Tables 4 and 5 and compared with the corresponding experimental obtained in Dimethyl sulfoxide-*d*₆ taken from (Ditchfield, 1974; SpectraBase, n.d.).

Table 4. Observed and Calculated ¹H Chemical Shifts (in ppm) for Conformers DAMN and DAFN in Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method				
Group	H Atoms	<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)	<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)	Experimental
				δ ppm (Multipl., Integ.)
NH ₂ (N3)	4	3.78	3.39	5.31 (s, 6H)
	5	3.35	3.71	
NH ₂ (N6)	7	3.78	3.39	
	8	3.35	3.71	
	RMSD	1.76	1.77	

Note: ^aThis work GIAO/B3LYP/6-311++G** Ref Ditchfield, 1974. to TMS,

^bFrom Ref SpectraBase, n.d.

Comparisons by using the RMSD values are presented in the two tables. For the ¹H nucleus, Table 4 shows a RMSDs value of 1.76 ppm for

DAMN and 1.77 ppm for DAFN, indicating that both species can be present in solution due to the similar values. The differences with the

experimental ones could be attributed to solvent due to that the calculations were performed in aqueous solution different from the experimental used Dimethyl sulfoxide-*d*₆. For the ¹³C nucleus, the value increase from 7.58

ppm for DAMN to 7.61 ppm for DAFN. We see that for the ¹H nucleus is observed a better correlation because the used method generate best results than the C atoms.

Table 5. Observed and Calculated ¹³C Chemical Shifts (δ in ppm) for Conformers DAMN and DAFN in Aqueous Solution by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method			
C Atoms	<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)	<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)	Experimental
			δ ppm
C1	115.25	116.80	107.24
C2	115.25	116.80	107.24
C9	124.53	122.35	117.40
C10	124.53	122.35	117.40
RMSD	7.58	7.61	

Note: ^aThis work GIAO/B3LYP/6-311++G** Ref Ditchfield, 1974. to TMS, ^bFrom Ref SpectraBase, n.d.

Moreover, the few differences found between both forms could indicate its presences in aqueous solution. These reasonable correlations in the RMSD values specify that the structures of both forms are appropriate to perform the vibrational studies.

Atomic Charges, MEP and Bond Orders

The properties observed in DAMN and DAFN forms, including mechanisms and sites of reaction could be explained by the existence of NH₂ and C≡N groups in its structures. Thus, for both forms, natural population atomic (NPA) and Merz-Kollman (MK) charges, MEP and bond orders (BO) have been predicted (Glendening, et al., 1996; Besler, Merz Jr., & Kollman, 1990). Hence, in Table 6 are presented the calculated MK and NPA charges on C, N and H atoms of *Cis* (DAMN) and *Trans* forms (DAFN) by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method while Table 7 shows the corresponding MEP and BOs values. Besides, Fig. 5 and 6

displays the variations on computed MK and NPA charges, respectively. Fig. 5 (lefts) shows that *Cis* and *Trans* forms in both media present similar variations but the N3 and N6 of NH₂ groups present most negative values in solution than N11 and N12 atoms of C≡N groups. In both cases the lower values are associated to the hydration of those groups by water molecules because the NH₂ groups are donor of H bonds while the C≡N groups acceptors of H bonds. Note that when the different forms are compared in both media by separate (rights), the similar variations on N atoms are observed. Regarding Fig. 6 it is observed that the NPA charges present similar behaviours than the MK ones and, some differences are observed on the C9, C10, N11 and N12 atoms in solution. The NPA charges on H atoms of both NH₂ groups in the two species show lower values in solution because they are the most labile atoms.

Table 6. Atomic Charges (NPA) and Merz-Kollman Charges for the Conformers Cis DAMN and Trans DAFN in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

B3LYP/ 6-311++G**Method								
Atoms	NPA				MK			
	Gas		PCM		Gas		PCM	
	<i>Cis</i>	<i>Trans</i>	<i>Cis</i>	<i>Trans</i>	<i>Cis</i>	<i>Trans</i>	<i>Cis</i>	<i>Trans</i>
1 C	0.042	0.033	0.039	0.035	0.109	-0.074	0.093	-0.035
2 C	0.042	0.033	0.039	0.035	0.115	-0.025	0.164	0.004
3 N	-0.786	-0.767	-0.787	-0.772	-0.726	-0.648	-0.813	-0.760
4 H	0.392	0.385	0.416	0.399	0.377	0.322	0.433	0.380
5 H	0.384	0.391	0.410	0.397	0.336	0.339	0.408	0.380
6 N	-0.787	-0.767	-0.787	-0.772	-0.717	-0.637	-0.807	-0.753
7 H	0.392	0.385	0.416	0.399	0.372	0.324	0.434	0.382
8 H	0.384	0.391	0.410	0.397	0.339	0.336	0.410	0.380
9 C	0.249	0.251	0.311	0.290	0.316	0.514	0.357	0.571
10 C	0.249	0.251	0.311	0.290	0.308	0.529	0.409	0.584
11 N	-0.281	-0.293	-0.389	-0.349	-0.417	-0.488	-0.535	-0.565
12 N	-0.281	-0.293	-0.389	-0.349	-0.412	-0.492	-0.552	-0.568

Table 7. Wiberg Bond Index and Calculated Molecular Electrostatic Potential (Atomic Units) for the Conformers DAMN and DAFN in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

DAMN B3LYP/ 6-311++G**Method								
Atoms	Wiberg Index				Electrostatic Potential			
	Gas		PCM		Gas		PCM	
	<i>Cis</i>	<i>Trans</i>	<i>Cis</i>	<i>Trans</i>	<i>Cis</i>	<i>Trans</i>	<i>Cis</i>	<i>Trans</i>
1 C	3.979	3.982	3.984	3.985	-14.667	-14.665	-14.653	-14.656
2 C	3.979	3.982	3.984	3.985	-14.667	-14.665	-14.653	-14.656
3 N	2.981	2.991	3.000	2.984	-18.340	-18.346	-18.316	-18.339
4 H	0.849	0.854	0.829	0.843	-0.992	-0.997	-0.960	-0.981
5 H	0.856	0.850	0.834	0.845	-0.990	-0.997	-0.946	-0.986
6 N	2.980	2.991	3.000	2.984	-18.340	-18.346	-18.316	-18.339
7 H	0.849	0.854	0.829	0.843	-0.992	-0.997	-0.960	-0.981
8 H	0.856	0.850	0.834	0.845	-0.990	-0.997	-0.946	-0.986
9 C	3.998	4.004	3.990	3.997	-14.730	-14.723	-14.726	-14.714
10 C	3.998	4.004	3.990	3.997	-14.730	-14.723	-14.726	-14.714
11 N	3.026	3.024	3.003	3.012	-18.397	-18.388	-18.428	-18.398
12 N	3.026	3.024	3.003	3.012	-18.397	-18.388	-18.428	-18.398

MK Charges

Figure 5. Variations of Calculated MK Charges Observed on C, N and H Atoms Corresponding to *Cis* and *Trans* forms Diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and Diaminofumaronitrile (DAFN) Calculated in Aqueous Solution with the B3LYP/6-311++G** method

NPA Charges

Figure 6. Variations Observed on Calculated NPA Charges on C, N and H Atoms Corresponding to *Cis* and *Trans* Forms Diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and Diaminofumaronitrile (DAFN) Calculated in Aqueous Solution with the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

Evaluating the MEP values from Table 7, the *Cis* form shows lower values on the N3 and N6 in both media but higher values on N11 and N12 in solution. On the contrary, the *Trans* form shows higher values on N3 and N6 but lower on N11 and N12. Such differences are justified by the highest solvation energy value of *Cis* form (-79.4062 kJ/mol). Hence, higher hydration is observed for the *Cis* one in solution, as supported by the less negative MEP values observed on H atoms because the two H atoms

of NH₂ groups are the most labile ones. The evaluations of the mapped MEP surfaces of both forms in gas phase, as revealed from Fig 7, show that the energy value in solution decrease from ± 0.061 a.u for the *Cis* form to ± 0.057 a.u for the *Trans* form. Thus, the nucleophilic sites on the N11 and N12 of both species are clearly observed of red colours while on the H atoms of NH₂ groups are electrophilic sites observed of blue colours. The inert regions correspond to sites with green colours.

Figure 7. Details of the Molecular Models for DAMN and DAFN in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method Showing the Geometries of All Their Bond Critical Points (BCPs)**

Analysing the bond orders (BO) totals by atom, as Wiberg bond index from Table 7, it is observed that the N11 and N2 of C≡N groups of two forms present the higher values, as expected due to the triple bonds. On the contrary, the *Cis* form show in solution higher values (N3 and N6) and lower values (N11 and N12) due to the hydration.

NBO and AIM Studies

Due to the presence of amine and cyanide groups, H bonds interactions are expected in both DAMN and DAFN species in both media and, for these reasons, NBO and AIM calculations have been performed by using the

NBO 3.1 and AIM 2000 programs (Glendening, et al., 1996; Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, et al., 2001). Hence, the donor-acceptor energy interactions $E(2)$ have been computed from the NBO calculations by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations. These energies for the two forms in both environments are given in Table 8. Thus, both forms have three different types of interactions, which are $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ and, where the higher energy values in both media are observed for the $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ interactions. The quick evaluations of total energy values show that the two DAMN and DAFN forms in aqueous solution have higher stabilities with values respectively of 744.9 and

687.9 kJ/mol while in the gas phase the *Trans* form (655.5 kJ/mol) is most stable than the *Cis* one (603.4 kJ/mol). Hence, both DAMN and

DAFN forms are stable in solution although the *Cis* form is the most stable one.

Table 8. Main Delocalization Energy (in kJ/mol) for the Conformers DAMN and DAFN in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

B3LYP/ 6-311++G**Method				
Delocalization	Gas		PCM	
	<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)	<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)	<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)	<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)
$\pi C1-C2 \rightarrow \pi^* C9-N11$	71.8	75.8	81.6	79.8
$\pi C1-C2 \rightarrow \pi^* C10-N12$	71.8	75.8	81.6	79.8
$\Delta ET_{\pi \rightarrow \pi^*}$	143.5	151.6	163.2	159.8
$LP(1)N3 \rightarrow \pi^* C1-C2$	92.3	110.2	110.9	107.1
$LP(1)N6 \rightarrow \pi^* C1-C2$	92.2	110.1	110.9	107.1
$LP(1)N11 \rightarrow \sigma^* C2-C9$	45.1	43.3	43.5	42.1
$LP(1)N12 \rightarrow \sigma^* C1-C10$	45.1	43.3	43.5	42.1
$\Delta ET_{LP \rightarrow \sigma^*}$	274.7	307.0	308.9	298.5
$\pi^* C1-C2 \rightarrow \pi^* C9-N11$	92.6	98.5	136.4	114.9
$\pi^* C1-C2 \rightarrow \pi^* C10-N12$	92.6	98.5	136.4	114.9
$\Delta ET_{\pi \rightarrow \pi^*}$	185.2	197.0	272.9	229.7
ΔET_{Total}	603.4	655.5	744.9	687.9

Analysing the stabilities from the topological properties with the AIM 2000 program, the electron density, the Laplacian values and the $|\lambda_1|/\lambda_3$ ratio are calculated in the bond critical points (BCPs) (Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, et al., 2001). Hence, those three parameters are presented in Table 9 (Appendix). The $|\lambda_1|/\lambda_3$ ratios are calculated with the eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix ($\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$). According to the AIM theory, when the $\lambda_1/\lambda_3 < 1$ ratio and $\nabla^2 \rho(r) > 0$ the interaction is ionic or polar covalent but, in this case, both DAMN and DAFN forms show $\nabla^2 \rho(r) < 0$ and λ_1/λ_3 values > 1 , with exception of C10-N12 and C9-N11 bonds of two forms in both media. Thus, those bonds are shared indicating covalently bonded atoms. However, the details of molecular models for DAMN and DAFN in both media show from Fig. 7 the BCPs for all bonds in red colours, with exception of some N-H bonds.

Frontier Orbitals Studies

According Parr and Pearson, from the differences between the frontiers orbitals can be

computed the gap values which can predict reactivities and behaviours of species in diverse media. Later, with the gap values different descriptors can be obtained (Pearson, 1986; Parr, von Szentpaly, & Liu, 1999). For DAMN and DAFN in both media, the descriptors predicted in gas phase and aqueous solution by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method are shown in Table 10 together with the equations used to compute the descriptors. Evaluating the gap values, we observed few differences in the gap values of two species in both media, however, it is evident that both forms in solution are more reactive than the corresponding in gas phase and, that the *Trans* form is most reactive in solution (3.9073 eV) than the *Cis* one (4.0565 eV) because it has lower gap. These results are in correlation with the lower stability observed by NBO study for the *Trans* form in solution and with the lower energy observed for this form from the mapped MEP surface (0.057 a.u.). In reference to the descriptors, clearly we observed that the higher value observed in the global electrophilicity index (ω) of *Trans* form in

solution (4.6344 eV) justify its higher reactivity in this medium. In Fig. 8 it is observed the participations of HOMO-LUMO for both forms in aqueous solution. The figure shows different characteristics of orbitals but slightly lower densities values are observed for the *Trans*

form, as supported by the AIM study. These slight differences in the HOMO-LUMO of both forms could justify the higher solvation energy observed for the *Cis* form in aqueous solution perhaps due to that the higher hydration stabilize this form.

Table 10. Frontier Molecular HOMO and LUMO Orbitals for Conformers DAMN and DAFN in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method				
Orbital (eV)	<i>Cis</i> DAMN		<i>Trans</i> DAFN	
	GAS	PCM	GAS	PCM
HOMO	-6.1160	-5.5525	-5.9408	-6.2090
LUMO	-1.7607	-1.4726	-1.8843	-2.3017
GAP	4.3553	4.0799	4.0565	3.9073
DESCRIPTORS				
(eV)	GAS	PCM	GAS	PCM
χ	3.9384	3.5126	3.9125	4.2554
μ	-3.9384	-3.5126	-3.9125	-4.2554
η	2.1776	2.0399	2.0282	1.9537
S	0.2296	0.2451	0.2465	0.2559
ω	3.5614	3.0241	3.7736	4.6344

Note: ^aThis work; $\chi = - [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\mu = [E(\text{LUMO}) + E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\eta = [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $S = \frac{1}{2}\eta$; $\omega = \mu^2/2\eta$

Figure 8. HOMO-LUMO and Gap Values for DAMN and DAFN Forms in Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Vibrational Study

Both structures of DAMN and DAFN are optimized with C_i symmetries by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations and due to the 12 atoms present in both forms a total of 30 vibration modes are expected for each species. The experimental IR spectrum of DAMN in the solid phase compared with the corresponding predicted for both species in the gas phase are presented in Fig. 9 while comparisons of Raman spectra are observed in Fig. 10 (SpectraBase,

Figure 9. Experimental Infrared Spectrum of *Cis* (DAMN) Form Compared with the Corresponding Predicted for *Cis* and *Trans* (DAFN) by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

On the other side, Table 11 shows observed and calculated wavenumbers and assignments for DAMN and DAFN in the gas phase by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations. The comparisons presented in Table 11 shows IR and Raman bands of both species, thus the bands at 1361 and 1371 cm^{-1} are assigned to C2-N3 stretching modes of DAFN while the bands at 1318 and 1324 cm^{-1} are predicted and assigned to NH_2 deformation mode of DAMN. In the same way, the Raman band at 647 cm^{-1} only can be assigned to out-of-plane deformation modes of C2-N3 and C1-N6 of DAMN (γC2N3 ,

n.d.). The predicted Raman spectra of both forms were corrected to intensities (Keresztury, et al., 1993). Fig. 9 show the very good correlations between the spectra of C_i form. To compute the harmonic force fields with the SQMFF methodology normal internal coordinates, transferable scaling factors and PED contributions $\geq 10\%$ have been employed to perform the complete assignments of DAMN and DAFN (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002)

Figure 10. Experimental Raman Spectrum of *Cis* (DAMN) Form Compared with the Corresponding Predicted for *Cis* and *Trans* (DAFN) by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

γC1N6) because for the DAFN form the calculations do not predict bands in this region. The IR and Raman bands between 3438 and 3296 cm^{-1} are assigned to antisymmetric and symmetric modes of NH_2 groups, as predict the calculations and as observed in species containing this group (Cataldo, et al., 2024; Sundius, & Brandán, 2023).

Then, the IR and Raman bands at 2205 and 2225 cm^{-1} , respectively are easily assigned to stretching modes of cyanide groups. The strong IR band respectively at 1649 and 1361 cm^{-1} are assigned

to C1-C2 and C2-N3 of DAMN and DAFN forms (Romani, & Brandán, 2024), respectively while the medium intensity IR band at 1240 cm⁻¹

can be assigned to C2-N3 and C1-N6 of DAMN and DAFN forms, respectively.

Table 11. Observed and Calculated Wavenumbers (cm⁻¹), Potential Energy Distribution and Assignment for DAMN and DAFN Forms in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Experimental ^c		B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a			
		<i>Cis</i> DAMN		<i>Trans</i> DAFN	
IR	Raman	SQM ^b	Assignments	SQM ^b	Assignments
3438 _s	3336 _{vw}	3493	v _a NH ₂ (N6)	3492	v _a NH ₂ (N3)
3374 _s	3263 _{vw}	3490	v _a NH ₂ (N3)	3491	v _a NH ₂ (N6)
3346 _{vs}	3189 _{vw}	3377	v _s NH ₂ (N6)	3396	v _s NH ₂ (N3)
3296 _{sb}		3372	v _s NH ₂ (N3)	3394	v _s NH ₂ (N6)
2205 _s	2225 _{vs}	2232	vC9-N11	2226	vC9-N11
		2231	vC10-N12	2223	vC10-N12
1649 _s		1604	vC1-C2	1602	vC1-C2
	1624 _m	1586	δNH ₂ (N3)	1581	δNH ₂ (N6)
1616 _s		1571	δNH ₂ (N6)	1568	δNH ₂ (N3)
1361 _s	1371 _w			1373	vC2-N3
1318 _m	1324 _{vw}	1344	ρNH ₂ (N3)		
1240 _m		1264	vC1-N6	1242	ρNH ₂ (N6)
1240 _m		1214	vC2-N3	1206	vC1-N6
1095 _w		1090	ρNH ₂ (N6)		
1049 _w				1073	ρNH ₂ (N3)
842 _w		939	vC1-C10	907	vC2-C9
724 _m		728	wagNH ₂ (N3)	719	vC2-N3, vC1-N6
	709 _w	673	vC2-C9	680	γC1N6, γC2N3
		670	wagNH ₂ (N6)	653	wagNH ₂ (N6)
	647 _w	635	γC2N3, γC1N6		
614 _m		600	wagNH ₂ (N6), wagNH ₂ (N3)	607	wagNH ₂ (N6), wagNH ₂ (N3)
				565	wagNH ₂ (N3)
	538 _w	517	δN11C9C2, δN12C10C1	555	δN11C9C2, δN12C10C1
513 _m		502	τ _w C1-C10, τ _w C2-C9	524	τ _w C1-C10, τ _w C2-C9
456 _w	471 _{vw}			454	ρC2N3, ρC1N6
		398	τ _w C2-C9, τ _w C1-C10	333	τ _w C1-C10, τ _w C2-C9
		364	τ _w NH ₂ (N6)	323	ρC2N3, ρC1N6
	311 _w	275	ρC2N3, ρC1N6	305	τ _w NH ₂ (N6)
	230 _w	216	δN12C10C1, δN11C9C2	225	γC2N3
		209	γC2N3, γC1N6	216	τ _w NH ₂ (N3)
	172 _w	117	δC10C1C2, δC9C2C1	167	δN12C10C1, δN11C9C2
		106	τ _w C2-C1	123	δC10C1C2, δC9C2C1
		100	τ _w NH ₂ (N3)	86	τ _w C2-C1

Note: ^aThis work, ^bFrom SQMFF/B3LYP/6-311++G** method, ^cFrom Ref SpectraBase, n.d. Abbreviations: v, stretching; β, deformation in the plane; γ, deformation out of plane; wag, wagging; τ, torsion; ρ, rocking; τ_w, twisting; δ, deformation; a, antisymmetric; s, symmetric.

The NH₂ deformation modes in both forms are assigned to 1624 and 1616 cm⁻¹, respectively while the rocking modes of both forms are assigned in different positions, as predicted by SQM calculations (Cataldo, et al., 2024; Sundius, & Brandán, 2023). Thus, those two modes in DAMN are assigned respectively at 1318 and 1095 cm⁻¹ while in DAFN are assigned at 1240 and 1049 cm⁻¹. The NH₂ wagging and twisting modes are predicted in DAMN respectively at 670/600 and 364/100 cm⁻¹ while in DAFN at 653/565 and 305/216 cm⁻¹. Hence, those two modes are assigned to the IR and Raman bands observed in those regions (Cataldo, et al., 2024;

Sundius, & Brandán, 2023). The remains skeletal modes are assigned as predicted by SQM calculations and as detailed in Table 11.

Force Constants

Scaled force constants for DAMN and DAFN forms have been calculated from the harmonic force fields (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). These constants for both forms in the two media by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** are shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Comparison of Scaled Internal Force Constants for DAMN and DAFN in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Force constant	B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a			
	Gas		PCM	
	<i>Cis</i> DAMN	<i>Trans</i> DAFN	<i>Cis</i> DAMN	<i>Trans</i> DAFN
$f(\nu_{\text{C-N}})$	5.790	5.845	6.416	5.672
$f(\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}})$	17.400	17.362	17.917	16.670
$f(\nu_{\text{C=C}})$	7.712	7.581	8.174	7.405
$f(\nu_{\text{C-C}})$	5.538	5.360	6.032	5.391
$f(\nu_{\text{NH}_2})$	6.546	6.587	7.080	6.388

Note: Units are mdyn Å⁻¹ for stretching. ^aThis work.

Table 12 show clear differences between DAMN and DAFN forms in aqueous solution. Hence, the five force constants for the DAMN form present higher values in solution indicating that this species is the most stable in this medium than DAFN, as supported by the NBO calculations and by the low reactivity predicted in water for this form. On the contrary, in gas the $f(\nu_{\text{NH}_2})$ and $f(\nu_{\text{C-N}})$ force constants associated to NH₂ and C-N groups of DAFN present values slightly higher than the DAMN form while the other constants show higher values in the DAMN form. The higher values in the scaled force constants of DAMN suggest the higher stability of this species in solution, as also supported by the lower values of corresponding geometrical parameters.

Electronic Spectra

The experimental electronic spectra of DAMN and DAFN in ethanol and ether-isopentane alcohol, respectively taken from Webb, Frank, & Schneider, (1955) and Becker, Kolc, & Rotham, (1973) are compared in Fig. 11 with the predicted for both forms in aqueous solution by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method. Both forms show only one band with different intensities, as observed from Table 13 together with the oscillator strength (f) for DAMN and DAFN forms.

Figure 11. Experimental Electronic Spectra of *Cis* (DAMN) and *Trans* (DAFN) Forms Compared with the Corresponding Predicted by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Thus, in the *Cis* form the band is located at 296 nm while in the *trans* form the band is observed at 314 nm. The predicted UV spectrum for DAMN show two bands at 177 and 273 nm while the *Trans* form shows two bands at 188 and 301 nm. Note that the experimental spectra are recorded from 200 to 450 nm and, for this reason, the predicted bands between 150 and 200 nm are not reported. In these species, the temperature and the solvent used is very important because it is necessary taking into account that a high quantum yield and a very small activation energy is observed for the *Cis* ↔ *Trans* photoisomerization (Becker, Kolc, & Rotham, 1973). The bands observed are associated to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, as predicted by NBO calculations.

Table 13. Calculated Bands of Absorption (nm) and Oscillator Strength (f) for DAMN and DAFN in Aqueous Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

B3LYP/6-311++G** method					
<i>Cis</i> DAMN					
Energy transition ^a (ev)	λ (nm)	f	Exp ^b	Exp ^c	Assigments
4.485	276.4	0.183	296	295	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
4.614	268.7	0.163			$n \rightarrow \sigma^*$
					$\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$
<i>Trans</i> DAFN					
Energy transition ^a (ev)	λ (nm)	f	Exp ^b	Exp ^c	Assigments
4.114	301.3	0.264	314		$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
					$n \rightarrow \sigma^*$
					$\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$

Note: ^aThis work, ^bFrom Becker, Kolc, & Rotham, (1973), ^cFrom Ref Webb, Frank, & Schneider, (1955)

Conclusions

In this investigation, hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations have been combined with scaled quantum mechanical force field (SQMF) methodology to perform the harmonic

force fields and force constants of prebiotic diaminomaleonitrile (DAMN) and diaminefumaronitrile (DAFN). Comparisons of predicted FT-IR, FT-Raman, ¹H-, ¹³C-NMR and UV-visible spectra with the experimental ones

show good correlations. Both IR and Raman spectra show bands related to both forms. Complete vibrational assignments are reported for both forms together with the main scaled force constants. NBO calculations reveal that both forms are stable in solution although the *Cis* form is the most stable one. The gap values suggest that both forms in solution are more reactive than the corresponding in gas phase and, that the *Trans* form presents higher reactivity in this medium. These results are in agreement with the lower stability observed by NBO study for the *Trans* form in solution and with the lower energy observed for this form from the mapped MEP surface. The higher values in the scaled force constants of DAMN suggest the higher stability of this species in solution, as also supported by the lower values of corresponding geometrical parameters.

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Author Contributions

María V. Castillo: Conceived and designed the analysis;

Elida Romano: Conceived and designed the analysis;

María E. Manzur: Analysed and interpreted the data;

Silvia Antonia Brandán: Conceived and designed the analysis; Analysed and interpreted the data; Wrote the paper.

All Authors have revised the paper.

Conflict Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest as concern this article.

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Table 9. An Analysis of the Bond Critical Points (BCP) for the Conformers DAMN and DAFN in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution

B3LYP/ 6-311++G* *Method														
Parameter (a.u.)	Gas													
	<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)							<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)						
	C1-C2	C1-N6	C1-C10	C2-N3	C2-C9	C10-	C9-N11	C1-C2	C1-N6	C1-	C2-N3	C2-C9	C10-	C9-
$\rho(r_c)$	0.3259	0.2974	0.2852	0.2974	0.2852	0.4762	0.4762	0.3219	0.3052	0.2863	0.3052	0.2863	0.4734	0.4734
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	-	-0.8563	-0.7839	-0.8563	-0.7840	-0.2799	-0.2799	-	-	-	-0.8931	-	-0.3513	-0.3512
λ_1	-	-0.6337	-0.5806	-0.6337	-0.5806	-1.0245	-1.0245	-	-	-	-0.6620	-	-1.0300	-1.0300
λ_2	-	-0.5488	-0.5161	-0.5489	-0.5162	-0.9971	-0.9971	-	-	-	-0.5655	-	-1.0015	-1.0015
λ_3	0.3126	0.3263	0.3128	0.3263	0.3128	1.7418	1.7418	0.3153	0.3344	0.3027	0.3344	0.3027	1.6802	1.6802
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	2.3225	1.9422	1.8561	1.9421	1.8562	0.5882	0.5882	2.2609	1.9794	1.9292	1.9796	1.9291	0.6130	0.6130
B3LYP/ 6-311++G* *Method														
Parameter (a.u.)	PCM													
	<i>Cis</i> (DAMN)							<i>Trans</i> (DAFN)						
	C1-C2	C1-N6	C1-C10	C2-N3	C2-C9	C10-	C9-N11	C1-C2	C1-N6	C1-	C2-N3	C2-C9	C10-	C9-
$\rho(r_c)$	0.3217	0.2996	0.2825	0.2996	0.2825	0.4764	0.4764	0.3209	0.3011	0.2838	0.3011	0.2839	0.4744	0.4744
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	-	-0.8647	-0.7728	-0.8648	-0.7729	-0.2967	-0.2967	-	-	-	-0.8690	-	-0.3298	-0.3298
λ_1	-	-0.6457	-0.5724	-0.6458	-0.5725	-1.0308	-1.0308	-	-	-	-0.6518	-	-1.0317	-1.0317
λ_2	-	-0.5517	-0.5090	-0.5517	-0.5091	-1.0072	-1.0072	-	-	-	-0.5588	-	-1.0064	-1.0064
λ_3	0.3128	0.3327	0.3087	0.3327	0.3087	1.7413	1.7413	0.3134	0.3416	0.3035	0.3416	0.3035	1.7084	1.7084
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	2.2670	1.9407	1.8544	1.9410	1.8546	0.5920	0.5920	2.2530	1.9081	1.8977	1.9081	1.8977	0.6039	0.6039